

Growth Mindset Profiles Among Senior High School Students: Academic Achievement and Stress Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This research utilized person-centered methodology to examine distinct configurations of growth mindset beliefs among Filipino senior high school students and examine their relationship with academic outcomes across different specializations, moving beyond traditional fixed-growth dichotomies. K-means clustering analysis was conducted with data from 1,043 Filipino senior high school students across four academic strands (STEM, ABM, HUMSS, GAS). Multinomial logistic regression examined predictors of profile membership, while moderation analyses tested contextual effects of academic strand and sex on profile-outcome relationships. Three distinct profiles emerged: Fixed Mindset (24.3%), Moderate Growth (47.7%), and Strong Growth (28.1%). Strong Growth students demonstrated significantly higher academic achievement ($M = 88.9$ vs. $88.1-88.2$, $p < .05$) and lower perceived stress ($M = 23.6$ vs. $24.9-25.6$, $p < .01$) compared to other profiles. Academic strand and sex predicted profile membership, with strand moderating the mindset-stress relationship specifically in STEM contexts. Notably, Moderate Growth students did not differ significantly from Fixed Mindset students on either outcome, suggesting a threshold effect for mindset benefits. This study extends growth mindset theory by revealing complex configurations of intelligence beliefs that function differently across educational contexts. These results underscore the necessity of examining both mindset orientations and educational context when designing interventions, suggesting mindset effects are context-dependent. The substantial Moderate Growth group represents a critical target for tailored interventions to strengthen partial growth beliefs into more robust mindset orientations.

Keywords: growth mindset, cluster analysis, academic achievement, academic stress, senior high school students

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INTRODUCTION

Growth mindset theory proposes that individuals' beliefs about the malleability of their abilities significantly impact their motivation, learning, and achievement (Kyler & Moscicki, 2024). Students with a growth mindset believe that intelligence and abilities can be developed through effort, effective strategies, and learning from feedback, whereas those with a fixed mindset view these qualities as largely innate and unchangeable (Kroeper et al., 2022). This distinction in mindset orientation has demonstrated meaningful implications for educational outcomes across diverse contexts, though recent systematic reviews reveal mixed results regarding intervention effectiveness (Gazmuri, 2025).

Despite advances in growth mindset research, the predominant variable-centered approach has limited the understanding of how mindset beliefs operate in real educational contexts. Variable-centered methods focus on average relationships between mindset and outcomes across entire samples, potentially obscuring meaningful patterns of individual differences (Laurell et al., 2025). Person-centered approaches, in contrast, can identify distinct subgroups of individuals with different configurations of mindset beliefs and examine how these profiles relate to important outcomes (Schel & Drechsel, 2025). Recent research suggests that students may not simply fall along a single continuum from fixed to growth mindset but instead may hold varying configurations of beliefs that function differently across contexts (Malespina et al., 2023).

The Philippine educational system underwent significant restructuring with the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program in 2013, which extended basic education to include senior high school (Grades 11-12) with specialized academic tracks. Within this context, Filipino students navigate a highly competitive educational environment characterized by strong cultural emphasis on academic achievement and family expectations (Yazon et al., 2021). Recent research by Co (2025) further confirms these distinctions, finding significant variations in how students across different academic strands evaluate educational implementation and faculty performance in technology-enhanced learning environments. Students choose from four specialized tracks: STEM, HUMSS, ABM, or GAS, each creating distinct learning environments with unique academic demands.

Research indicates that Filipino students experience significant academic stress, with rates comparable to or exceeding those in other Asian educational systems. Recent studies have shown promising associations between growth mindset and academic resilience among Filipino students (Calingasan & Plata, 2022; Repuya & Esterninos, 2022), yet little research has examined how mindset beliefs might function differently across academic strands or between different student groups using person-centered approaches.

Given the complex interaction between mindset beliefs, educational outcomes, and cultural context, substantial knowledge gaps persist regarding how growth mindset manifests among Filipino students across different academic specializations and demographic groups. Building on recent advances in person-centered mindset research (Laurell et al., 2025; Schel & Drechsel, 2025) and the need for culturally sensitive research, this study employs K-means clustering to identify distinct profiles of growth mindset beliefs among Filipino senior high school students. The present research addresses these specific questions:

1. What distinct growth mindset profiles emerge among Filipino senior high school students, and what demographic and academic factors predict membership in these profiles?
2. How do these profiles differ in academic achievement and perceived stress, and what is the magnitude and precision of these differences as indicated by effect size confidence intervals?
3. Do academic strand and sex independently moderate the relationship between mindset profiles and student outcomes?

By addressing these questions, this study contributes to both theoretical understanding of mindset beliefs in diverse cultural contexts and practical applications for supporting student success across different academic specializations in the Philippine educational system.

Literature Review

Person-Centered Approaches to Mindset Research

Person-centered analytical approaches have emerged as powerful tools in educational psychology, allowing researchers to identify distinct subgroups or profiles within heterogeneous populations. This method offers advantages over traditional variable-centered approaches by capturing the multidimensional nature of psychological constructs like mindset beliefs (Schel & Drechsel, 2025). Recent research has applied these techniques to examine mindset constructs across diverse educational settings, revealing complex patterns that challenge the simple fixed-growth dichotomy.

Laurell et al. (2025) identified four distinct mindset profiles among Finnish lower-secondary students using latent profile analysis: Growth, Fixed, Mixed, and Opposing profiles. The Opposing profile was particularly noteworthy, exhibiting malleable beliefs about intelligence and creativity while maintaining static views of giftedness, and showed superior performance in mathematics and foreign languages. This finding demonstrates the complexity of mindset beliefs and their domain-specific variations.

Similarly, Malespina et al. (2023) found that intelligence mindsets among bioscience students could be divided into four separable but correlated constructs: beliefs about one's own ability, one's own growth potential, others' ability, and others' growth potential. These findings support the notion that mindset beliefs are more nuanced than traditional fixed-growth dichotomies suggest.

Mindset Profiles and Academic Outcomes

Research using person-centered approaches has revealed important insights into how different mindset profiles relate to academic achievement and psychological well-being. Recent studies have demonstrated that mindset effects are not uniform across all students, with intervention effectiveness varying based on individual characteristics and contextual factors (Gazmuri, 2025; Burnette et al., 2022).

The relationship between mindset profiles and academic stress has received increased attention, particularly during challenging periods such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Mosanya (2021) found that growth mindset served as a protective factor against academic stress among international students during social isolation, with hierarchical regression models explaining 36% of variance in academic stress. Similarly, Zhao et al. (2023) identified three distinct stress trajectory profiles among Chinese first-year college students, with growth mindset contributing to more adaptive stress patterns during the transition to college.

Meyer and Stutts (2024) examined the effectiveness of combined mindset interventions, finding that synergistic interventions targeting both growth mindset and stress-is-enhancing mindset were most effective in improving student outcomes. These findings suggest that comprehensive approaches to mindset development may be more beneficial than single-domain interventions.

Cultural and Contextual Factors

Emerging research emphasizes that contextual variables may influence the association between mindset configurations and educational outcomes, including academic specialization and cultural background. Yeh et al. (2023) demonstrated that creativity mindset interventions could be enhanced through well-scaffolded educational games, with self-determination mediating the influence of growth mindset on creativity self-efficacy.

In the Philippine context specifically, recent research has explored growth mindset effects among Filipino students. Calingasan and Plata (2022) found that effort praise led Filipino ESL students to endorse different mindset orientations depending on the feedback context, with positive rule groups adopting growth mindsets while inverse rule groups adopted fixed mindsets. Repuya and Esterninos (2022) demonstrated that supplementary materials incorporating growth mindset principles could effectively elevate students' procedural fluency in mathematics and facilitate shifts from fixed to growth mindsets.

Yazon et al. (2021) conducted a correlational study examining mindset, grit, and adversity quotient among pre-service teachers in the Philippines and Hong Kong, finding that students with growth mindsets displayed higher levels of grit and adversity quotients than those with fixed mindsets. These studies highlight the cultural relevance of mindset research in Southeast Asian educational contexts.

Methodological Advances and Intervention Effectiveness

Recent systematic reviews have raised critical concerns regarding the efficacy of growth mindset programs. Gazmuri (2025) conducted a comprehensive review of 24 randomized controlled trials and found that the strongest studies exhibited null or very small effect sizes (Cohen's $d = -0.01$ to $+0.065$). These results indicate that mindset-based programs could have more modest effects than initially believed, particularly when implemented at scale.

However, Burnette et al. (2022) developed a Framework for the Implementation of Mindset Interventions (FIMI) that emphasizes the importance of implementation fidelity and contextual adaptation. Their systematic review suggests that intervention effectiveness may depend heavily on how interventions are designed and implemented rather than the underlying theoretical principles.

Kyler and Moscicki (2024) conducted a systematic review documenting the proliferation of mindset domains studied between 1995 and 2022, identifying the need for more research on mindset domain relationships and their implications for intervention design. They argue that the domain used in intervention messaging may be an understudied moderator of intervention efficacy.

Research Gaps and Study Rationale

Despite growing interest in person-centered approaches to mindset research, several gaps remain. First, the majority of person-centered mindset investigations have focused on Western and East Asian populations, leaving minimal research examining mindset profiles in Southeast Asian educational systems. Second, few studies have examined how mindset profiles might function differently across specialized academic tracks within the same educational system. Third, minimal studies have examined how personal variables like sex and academic specialization might predict mindset profile membership in diverse cultural contexts.

The current study addresses these gaps by examining mindset profiles among Filipino senior high school students across different academic strands using K-means clustering analysis, providing insights into how cultural and contextual factors shape the manifestation and effects of mindset beliefs in this unique educational context.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Sample

The investigation utilized a cross-sectional correlational methodology using a person-centered analytical approach. Participants included 1,043 Filipino senior high school students (Grade 11: $n = 546$, 52.3%; Grade 12: $n = 497$, 47.7%) attending a private school in Metro Manila, Philippines. The sample comprised 638 females (61.2%), 390 males (37.4%), and 15 students who preferred not to specify sex (1.4%), aged 15-20+ years ($M = 16.8$, $SD = 0.67$). Students were

enrolled across four specialized tracks: STEM (n = 634, 60.8%), ABM (n = 178, 17.1%), HUMSS (n = 149, 14.3%), and GAS (n = 82, 7.9%). The socioeconomic background of participants was predominantly middle to upper-middle class, reflecting the typical demographic of private schools in Metro Manila.

Instrumentation

Growth Mindset Beliefs were assessed using a three-item adaptation of implicit theories of intelligence measures commonly used in mindset research (e.g., "You can always substantially change how intelligent you are") assessed using a 6-point response format (1 = strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree). Elevated scores reflect more robust growth mindset orientations. Internal reliability was satisfactory for this sample (Cronbach's $\alpha = .795$, McDonald's $\omega = .810$).

Academic achievement was assessed through students' General Weighted Average (GWA) retrieved from institutional academic records with appropriate permissions. GWA is calculated on a 100-point scale in the Philippine educational system, where elevated scores reflect superior academic achievement. The GWA represents the average of grades across all subject areas, weighted according to the number of units per subject.

Perceived Stress was assessed using the 10-item Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10; Cohen et al., 1983). The PSS-10 measures the extent to which life circumstances are perceived as stressful using a 5-point response format (0 = never, 4 = very often). Composite scores span 0-40, where elevated values reflect increased stress perception. The instrument demonstrated satisfactory reliability within the current sample (Cronbach's $\alpha = .773$, McDonald's $\omega = .782$).

Demographic Variables included age, grade level, sex, and academic specialization (STEM, HUMSS, ABM, or GAS).

Data Collection

Data gathering occurred throughout the second term of academic year 2023-2024 after securing necessary approvals from the school administration and school review board. Students completed online questionnaires during regular class hours under the supervision of trained homeroom advisers. Completion time averaged 10-15 minutes. Academic achievement data were obtained from school records with appropriate permissions and matched to survey responses.

Data Analysis

Data analysis proceeded in several phases using jamovi software (version 2.6.26). First, preliminary analyses examined descriptive statistics, scale reliability, and correlations using Spearman's rank correlation due to non-normal distributions (all Shapiro-Wilk tests $p < .001$).

K-means clustering analysis was conducted on the three mindset items to identify distinct profiles, testing 2-5 cluster solutions following recent methodological recommendations (Ghafari et al., 2025). The optimal solution was selected based on interpretability, adequate cluster sizes ($\geq 20\%$ of sample), variance explained (between-cluster sum of squares/total sum of squares), and theoretical meaningfulness. Profile membership variables were created using cutoff scores derived from cluster centroids. Multinomial logistic regression examined demographic and academic predictors of profile membership, with age as a covariate and grade level, sex, and academic strand as factors. Welch's ANOVA with Games-Howell post-hoc tests examined profile differences in outcomes, using robust methods appropriate for unequal group sizes and normality violations.

General Linear Models tested two separate moderation hypotheses: (1) Profile \times Academic Strand, and (2) Profile \times Sex, with age as a covariate. Effect sizes were calculated using partial η^2 with 95% confidence intervals. Three-way interactions were not feasible due to sparse cell counts in the unbalanced design (60.8% STEM students).

All analyses used a significance level of $p < .05$, with effect size interpretations following Cohen's conventions (small: $\eta^2 = .01$, medium: $\eta^2 = .06$, large: $\eta^2 = .14$).

Ethical Considerations

All research procedures received school review board approval and were performed following established ethical standards for human subjects research. Parental consent and student assent were obtained before data gathering commenced. Students were advised of their voluntary participation and withdrawal rights without consequences, and anonymity was maintained to all students when matching survey responses with academic records. All data were stored securely with restricted access.

RESULTS

The final sample shown in table 1 comprised 1,043 Filipino senior high school students distributed across grades 11 ($n = 546$, 52.3%) and 12 ($n = 497$, 47.7%), spanning 15-20+ years of age ($M = 16.8$, $SD = 0.67$). Participants were predominantly female ($n = 638$, 61.2%), with 390 males (37.4%) and 15 students (1.4%) who preferred not to specify their sex. Academic strand distribution reflected the institution's focus, with 634 students (60.8%) enrolled in STEM, 178 (17.1%) in ABM, 149 (14.3%) in HUMSS, and 82 (7.9%) in GAS programs.

Table 1. Participant Demographics and Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Category/Statistic	Value	
Sample Size	N	1,043	
Grade Level	Grade 11, n (%)	546 (52.3%)	
	Grade 12, n (%)	497 (47.7%)	
Age	M (SD)	16.8 (0.67)	
	Range	15-20+ years	
Sex	Female, n (%)	638 (61.2%)	
	Male, n (%)	390 (37.4%)	
	Prefer not to say, n (%)	15 (1.4%)	
Academic Strand	STEM, n (%)	634 (60.8%)	
	ABM, n (%)	178 (17.1%)	
	HUMSS, n (%)	149 (14.3%)	
	GAS, n (%)	82 (7.9%)	
Scale Reliability			
	Mindset Scale	Cronbach's α (McDonald's ω)	.795 (.810)
	Stress Scale (PSS-10)	Cronbach's α (McDonald's ω)	.773 (.782)
Outcome Variables			
	Academic Achievement (GWA)	M (SD)	88.4 (3.66)
	Perceived Stress	M (SD)	24.7 (5.24)

Both measurement scales demonstrated acceptable reliability. The three-item growth mindset scale showed good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .795$, McDonald's $\omega = .810$), as did the PSS-10 stress scale (Cronbach's $\alpha = .773$, McDonald's $\omega = .782$). Academic achievement, measured by General Weighted Average (GWA), averaged 88.4 ($SD = 3.66$) on a 100-point scale, indicating generally high performance levels across the sample. Perceived stress scores averaged 24.7 ($SD = 5.24$) on the 40-point PSS-10 scale, suggesting moderate stress levels among participants.

All variables violated normality assumptions based on Shapiro-Wilk tests (all $p < .001$), justifying the use of non-parametric correlations and robust statistical methods in subsequent analyses. Preliminary Spearman correlations revealed theoretically consistent patterns: small but significant negative associations between mindset scores and stress ($r_s = -.103$ to $-.116$, $ps < .001$) and positive associations between mindset scores and academic achievement ($r_s = .057$ to $.143$, $ps < .001$ to $.065$).

Mindset Profile Identification and Predictors

K-means clustering analysis testing 2-5 cluster solutions revealed that a three-profile solution provided the optimal balance of interpretability, theoretical meaningfulness, and statistical fit. This solution explained 58.7% of the total variance in mindset beliefs (between-cluster SS = 2,942, total SS = 5,013) and yielded three distinct profiles with adequate sample sizes.

The Fixed Mindset profile (n = 253, 24.3%) was characterized by consistently low scores across all mindset items (centroids: 2.31, 2.28, 2.03), indicating strong beliefs that intelligence is largely unchangeable. The Moderate Growth profile (n = 497, 47.7%) represented the largest group, with moderate endorsement of growth beliefs (centroids: 3.49, 3.61, 3.30). The Strong Growth profile (n = 293, 28.1%) demonstrated consistently high scores across all items (centroids: 4.78, 5.05, 4.81), reflecting strong beliefs in the malleability of intelligence (Table 2).

Table 2. Three-Profile Solution from K-means Clustering Analysis

Profile	n (%)	Mindset Item 1	Mindset Item 2	Mindset Item 3	Profile Description
Fixed Mindset	253 (24.3%)	2.31	2.28	2.03	Consistently low scores across all mindset items
Moderate Growth	497 (47.7%)	3.49	3.61	3.30	Moderate scores reflecting partial growth beliefs
Strong Growth	293 (28.1%)	4.78	5.05	4.81	Consistently high scores reflecting strong growth beliefs

Profile validation confirmed significant differences across all three mindset items (all ps < .001), with observed means closely matching the derived cluster centroids, supporting the validity of the clustering solution.

Multinomial logistic regression examined demographic and academic predictors of profile membership, using Fixed Mindset as the reference category. The overall model demonstrated significant fit ($\chi^2 = 30.3$, df = 14, p = .007) with modest explanatory power ($R^2_{McFadden} = .014$) and approximately 52% classification accuracy shown in Table 3.

Sex emerged as a significant predictor for Moderate Growth profile membership. Compared to Fixed Mindset students, females were significantly more likely than males to belong to the Moderate Growth profile (OR = 1.401, 95% CI [1.013, 1.934], p = .041). However, sex did not significantly predict Strong Growth profile membership (OR = 0.998, 95% CI [0.702, 1.420], p = .993).

Academic strand showed the strongest predictive effects. Students in the General Academic Strand (GAS) were significantly showed greater probability of Moderate Growth profile membership compared to ABM students (OR = 4.646, 95% CI [2.102, 10.268], p < .001). This large effect size suggests that the broader, less specialized nature of the GAS curriculum may foster more malleable views of intelligence. Other strand comparisons (HUMSS vs. ABM, STEM vs. ABM) approached significance but did not reach conventional thresholds.

Age and grade level did not significantly predict profile membership, suggesting that mindset beliefs are relatively stable across the senior high school years in this sample.

Table 3. Multinomial Logistic Regression Predicting Mindset Profile Membership

Predictor	Moderate Growth vs. Fixed			Strong Growth vs. Fixed		
	OR	95% CI	p	OR	95% CI	p
Age	1.063	[0.820, 1.379]	.643	1.080	[0.811, 1.437]	.600
Grade Level (Grade 12 vs. 11)	0.791	[0.525, 1.192]	.263	0.738	[0.469, 1.160]	.188
Sex						
Male vs. Female	0.714	[0.517, 0.987]	.041*	0.998	[0.702, 1.420]	.993
Prefer not to say vs. Female	0.723	[0.174, 3.001]	.655	1.576	[0.385, 6.459]	.527
Academic Strand						
GAS vs. ABM	4.646	[2.102, 10.268]	<.001***	2.137	[0.858, 5.324]	.103

HUMSS vs. ABM	1.529	[0.889, 2.628]	.125	1.461	[0.798, 2.675]	.219
STEM vs. ABM	1.389	[0.928, 2.079]	.110	1.460	[0.931, 2.291]	.099

Model Fit: $\chi^2 = 30.3$, $df = 14$, $p = .007$; R^2 McFadden = .014

Note. N = 1,043. OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval. Reference categories: Fixed Mindset profile; Female sex; ABM academic strand. * $p < .05$, *** $p < .001$.

Profile Differences in Academic Achievement and Stress

In Table 4, Welch's ANOVA revealed significant differences in academic achievement across mindset profiles, $F(2, 594) = 4.55$, $p = .011$, with a small effect size ($\eta^2 = .008$). Post-hoc analyses using Games-Howell tests revealed that Strong Growth students significantly outperformed both other groups. Strong Growth students ($M = 88.9$, $SD = 3.46$) achieved higher GWA scores than Fixed Mindset students ($M = 88.1$, $SD = 3.57$; mean difference = 0.81, $p = .022$, $d = 0.23$) and Moderate Growth students ($M = 88.2$, $SD = 3.79$; mean difference = 0.68, $p = .027$, $d = 0.19$). Notably, Fixed and Moderate Growth profiles did not differ significantly in academic achievement (mean difference = -0.13, $p = .897$), suggesting that partial endorsement of growth mindset beliefs may be insufficient to confer academic benefits.

Table 4. Profile Differences in Academic Achievement and Perceived Stress

Outcome	Fixed Mindset (n = 253)	Moderate Growth (n = 497)	Strong Growth (n = 293)	F	p	η^2
Academic Achievement						
M (SD)	88.1 (3.57)	88.2 (3.79)	88.9 (3.46)	4.55	.011	.008
Perceived Stress						
M (SD)	25.6 (5.07)	24.9 (4.96)	23.6 (5.66)	9.54	< .001	.020

Note. F-statistics from Welch's ANOVA. Academic Achievement measured on 100-point scale; Perceived Stress measured on 40-point PSS-10 scale. Cohen's d effect sizes reported for significant comparisons.

Mindset profiles differed significantly in perceived stress levels, $F(2, 566) = 9.54$, $p < .001$, with a small to medium effect size ($\eta^2 = .020$). The pattern of differences paralleled achievement outcomes but with larger effect sizes. Strong Growth students reported significantly lower stress ($M = 23.6$, $SD = 5.66$) compared to both Fixed Mindset students ($M = 25.6$, $SD = 5.07$; mean difference = 1.97, $p < .001$, $d = 0.38$) and Moderate Growth students ($M = 24.9$, $SD = 4.96$; mean difference = 1.28, $p = .004$, $d = 0.25$). Again, Fixed and Moderate Growth profiles did not differ significantly in stress levels (mean difference = 0.69, $p = .176$), reinforcing the pattern suggesting a threshold effect for mindset benefits.

Independent Moderation Effects

Two separate general linear models tested whether academic strand moderated the relationship between mindset profiles and student outcomes, controlling for age as seen in table 5.

For academic achievement, the Profile \times Academic Strand interaction was non-significant, $F(6, 1018) = 0.223$, $p = .970$, $\eta^2 p = .001$, indicating that the achievement benefits of Strong Growth mindset were consistent across all academic specializations.

Table 5. Moderation Analysis Results

Analysis	Outcome	Interaction	F	df	p	$\eta^2 p$	Result
Profile \times Academic Strand							
	Academic Achievement	Profile \times Strand	0.223	6, 1018	.970	.001	Non-significant
	Perceived Stress	Profile \times Strand	3.49	6, 1018	.002	.020	Significant

Profile × Sex						
Academic Achievement	Profile × Sex	1.05	4, 1021	.382	.004	Non-significant
Perceived Stress	Profile × Sex	0.324	4, 1021	.862	.001	Non-significant

Note. η^2p = partial eta-squared. Effect size interpretations: .01 = small, .06 = medium, .14 = large. Simple effects analysis conducted only for significant interactions.

For perceived stress, a significant Profile × Academic Strand interaction emerged, $F(6, 1018) = 3.49$, $p = .002$, $\eta^2p = .020$. Simple effects analysis revealed that the stress-buffering effects of growth mindset were most pronounced in STEM contexts. Among STEM students, both Moderate Growth ($\beta = -2.024$, $SE = 1.005$, $p = .044$) and Strong Growth students showed significantly lower stress compared to Fixed Mindset students. However, these protective effects were less consistent or non-significant in ABM, HUMSS, and GAS strands.

This pattern suggests that growth mindset beliefs may be particularly valuable for stress management in STEM academic contexts, where students frequently encounter challenging problems and setbacks that require persistence and resilience.

Profile × Sex interactions were non-significant for both outcomes: academic achievement, $F(4, 1021) = 1.05$, $p = .382$, $\eta^2p = .004$; perceived stress, $F(4, 1021) = 0.324$, $p = .862$, $\eta^2p = .001$. These results indicate that the benefits associated with different mindset profiles operate similarly for male and female students in this cultural and educational context.

DISCUSSIONS

Profile Characteristics and Theoretical Implications

This study identified three distinct mindset profiles among Filipino senior high school students, extending beyond the traditional fixed-growth dichotomy and supporting the theoretical value of person-centered approaches to mindset research. The emergence of a substantial Moderate Growth profile (47.7%) aligns with recent findings by Laurell et al. (2025) who identified similar heterogeneity in mindset beliefs among Finnish students, suggesting that nearly half of students hold intermediate beliefs about intelligence malleability that represent an important target for intervention efforts.

The three-profile solution differs from some recent studies finding four or more profiles (Laurell et al., 2025; Malespina et al., 2023), possibly reflecting cultural differences in how mindset beliefs are conceptualized or the specific educational context of the Philippine K-12 system. The dominance of growth-oriented profiles (75.8% in either Moderate or Strong Growth categories) is consistent with recent research in collectivist cultural contexts (Yazon et al., 2021), while the meaningful minority with Fixed beliefs (24.3%) indicates important heterogeneity that warrants attention.

Achievement and Stress Outcomes

The finding that Strong Growth profiles demonstrated advantages in both academic achievement and stress management supports theoretical frameworks linking growth mindset to positive academic and psychological outcomes (Kroeper et al., 2022). However, the small effect sizes ($\eta^2 = .008$ for achievement, $.020$ for stress) align with recent meta-analyses suggesting modest effects of mindset interventions (Gazmuri, 2025). These effect sizes, while small, represent educationally meaningful differences when considered across large student populations, consistent with current debates about the practical significance of mindset effects (Kyler & Moscicki, 2024).

A particularly important finding was that Moderate Growth students did not differ significantly from Fixed Mindset students in academic achievement, suggesting a possible threshold effect where partial endorsement of growth mindset may be insufficient to confer

academic benefits. This pattern has significant implications for intervention design, aligning with recent recommendations for comprehensive mindset development rather than surface-level interventions (Burnette et al., 2022). The finding that Strong Growth students outperformed both other groups suggests that comprehensive mindset development may be necessary for academic benefits to emerge.

Contextual Moderation Effects

The differential moderation patterns for academic strand—significant for stress but not achievement—suggest that while the cognitive benefits of growth mindset appear relatively universal across academic contexts, the psychological experience varies by educational specialization. The finding that stress-buffering effects were most pronounced in STEM contexts aligns with recent research suggesting that beliefs about ability malleability may be particularly relevant in domains where students commonly encounter challenging problems and setbacks (Malespina et al., 2023). STEM coursework often involves complex problem-solving where persistence through difficulty is crucial, making growth mindset beliefs especially valuable for stress management in these contexts.

The non-significant sex moderation effects contrast with some research showing gender differences in mindset effects (Malespina et al., 2023), possibly reflecting cultural differences in how mindset beliefs manifest across genders in collectivist contexts. This finding suggests that in the Philippine educational context, growth mindset benefits operate similarly for male and female students, which has positive implications for intervention design.

Predictors of Profile Membership

The finding that academic strand and sex predict mindset profile membership has important implications for understanding how educational and social contexts shape psychological beliefs. The higher likelihood of growth-oriented profiles among females and students in certain academic strands (particularly GAS) suggests that mindset beliefs may be influenced by social and cultural factors within educational environments. The strong effect of GAS strand membership on Moderate Growth profile likelihood (OR = 4.646) may reflect the broader, less specialized nature of this track, which might foster more malleable views of intelligence.

Implications for Intervention Design

These findings have important implications for mindset intervention design in light of recent concerns about intervention effectiveness (Gazmuri, 2025). The identification of distinct profiles suggests that interventions should be tailored to address the specific characteristics of different groups rather than applying universal approaches. The substantial Moderate Growth group may benefit from interventions that strengthen and consolidate existing growth beliefs rather than introducing basic concepts, while Fixed Mindset students may require more comprehensive interventions.

The context-dependent nature of mindset effects, particularly for stress outcomes, suggests that interventions should consider academic specialization. For STEM students, interventions might emphasize the relevance of growth mindset for managing challenging problem-solving situations, while for students in other strands, different contextual framings may be more appropriate.

CONCLUSIONS

This study employed K-means clustering to identify three distinct mindset profiles among Filipino senior high school students, revealing meaningful heterogeneity that extends beyond traditional fixed-growth dichotomies. The Strong Growth profile consistently demonstrated advantages in both academic achievement and stress management, while the predominant Moderate Growth profile showed intermediate outcomes that did not significantly differ from Fixed profiles. Academic strand and sex emerged as significant predictors of profile membership, with strand moderating the mindset-stress relationship in context-specific ways.

The findings suggest that mindset interventions should be tailored to address the specific characteristics of different profiles and consider the educational context in which they are implemented. The substantial Moderate Growth group represents a particularly important target for intervention, as these students show partial endorsement of growth beliefs but may benefit from support to develop stronger, more consistent mindset orientations. The context-dependent nature of mindset effects, particularly for stress outcomes, highlights the importance of considering academic specialization when designing intervention programs.

These results contribute to our theoretical understanding of how mindset beliefs manifest in diverse cultural and educational contexts while providing practical insights for intervention design in the Philippine educational system. The person-centered approach successfully revealed meaningful individual differences that would be obscured by traditional variable-centered methods, supporting its continued use in educational psychology research and emphasizing the necessity of examining personal variations and environmental influences when comprehending psychological constructs.

Several limitations should be noted when evaluating these results. The cross-sectional methodology precludes causal conclusions about mindset development or outcomes, and the sample was drawn from a single private institution with predominantly middle-to-upper socioeconomic students, limiting generalizability to public schools or more diverse socioeconomic contexts. The unbalanced academic strand distribution (60.8% STEM) restricted complex interaction analyses and may have influenced the pattern of results. Additionally, the modest effect sizes observed, while statistically significant, suggest that mindset profiles explain only a small portion of variance in academic achievement and stress outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The identification of distinct mindset profiles suggests that educational interventions should be tailored to address the specific characteristics of different student groups rather than applying universal approaches. For students in the Fixed Mindset profile, comprehensive interventions that introduce fundamental concepts about intelligence malleability may be necessary. Students in the Moderate Growth profile, representing nearly half of the sample, may benefit from interventions that strengthen and consolidate existing growth beliefs rather than introducing basic concepts. The context-dependent nature of mindset effects suggests that interventions should consider academic specialization when designing implementation strategies. For STEM students, interventions might emphasize the specific relevance of growth mindset for managing challenging problem-solving situations, while for students in other academic strands, different contextual framings may be more appropriate. Educational institutions should also consider how structural and cultural factors within different academic programs might influence mindset development, as the finding that GAS students were more likely to hold Moderate Growth beliefs suggests that broader, less specialized curricula may naturally foster more malleable views of intelligence.

Future research should employ longitudinal designs to track mindset profile stability and change over time, examine mindset profiles across diverse educational contexts (public schools,

different socioeconomic levels), and investigate intervention approaches tailored to specific profile characteristics. Additionally, qualitative research could provide deeper insights into the experiences and beliefs underlying each profile, following recent recommendations for mixed-methods approaches in mindset research. Given recent concerns about intervention effectiveness, future studies should also examine whether profile-based interventions show greater effectiveness than traditional universal approaches, and whether the modest effect sizes observed in this study can be enhanced through more targeted, contextualized interventions that acknowledge the heterogeneity in students' mindset beliefs and the contextual factors that influence their expression.

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